

Synthesis of **norDTCO, 3, 7-dithiatricyclo[6.4.0.0^{2,10}.0^{9,11}]dodecane (norDTCO)**.

Dichloronorbornyldisulfide (114 mg, 0.50 mmol) was placed in a dry 3-necked flask equipped with a gas inlet, Dry-Ice condenser, and magnetic stir bar encased in glass under an argon atmosphere. The flask was cooled in a dry ice-acetone bath and ammonia let in through the gas inlet was condensed in the flask (about 30 mL). Sodium metal (92 mg, 4.0 mmol) was added in small pieces and at the end of the addition the solution was stirred at -30 to -40°C for 1-2h. The ammonia was removed by slow evaporation and the last residues removed by passing argon through the flask. Degassed aqueous tetrahydrofuran (THF) (40% v/v, 50 mL) was added followed by the addition of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (20 mg, 0.05 mmol). The flask was then equipped with a reflux condenser and addition funnel while maintaining an argon atmosphere. A solution of 1,3-dibromopropane (106 mg, 0.53 mmol) dissolved in degassed, dried, and distilled THF (10 mL) was added dropwise through the addition funnel. After completion of the addition the cloudy solution was stirred and heated at reflux for 2 h, with a heating mantel. The cooled mixture was transferred to a separatory funnel with the additional THF (100 mL). The aqueous phase was saturated with NaCl and the layers separated. The aqueous phase was extracted with THF (3 x 25 mL) and the combined THF extracts were concentrated using a rotary evaporator using a water bath. The liquid residue was extracted with chloroform (4 x 35 mL) and the extracts dried (anhydrous MgSO₄), filtered, and concentrated on a rotary evaporator with a water bath to a yellow oil. Distillation afforded pure **norDTCO** (85 mg, 85% yield) which solidified.

Synthesis and properties of **norDTCO sulfoxide**

3λ⁴, 7-dithiatricyclo[6.4.0.0^{2,10}.0^{9,11}]dodecan-3-one, norDTCO Sulfoxide. The dithioether, **norDTCO** (33 mg, 0.17 mmol) was dissolved in methanol (2 mL). A solution of NaIO₄ (39 mg, 0.18 mmol) dissolved in 1:1 aqueous MeOH (2 mL) was added dropwise to the dithioether with ice-water cooling. After completion of the addition, the mixture was stirred for 2 h. The methanol was then removed using a rotary evaporator and a water bath. The residue was diluted with water (10 mL) and extracted with ethyl acetate (EtOAc) (3 x 15 mL). The extracts were combined, dried (anhydrous MgSO₄), filtered, and concentrated on a rotary evaporator and a water bath. The residue was purified by preparative TLC on silica gel eluting with 30% methanol-ethylacetate to give **norDTCO sulfoxide** (25 mg, 70% yield) as a oily 5:1 mixture of diastereomers as determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopic analysis: ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.71 (dt J=3.0, 13.6 Hz) minor isomer. In addition to all the peaks for the major isomer, peaks for the minor isomer showed a 5:1 ratio of isomers, but complete assignments could not be made due to the overlap of peaks.